

Samen aanjagen van vernieuwing

Comparing the SURF pilot node with the EOSC EU Node

Author	Mark van de Sanden (SURF, Enterprise Architect)
Contributors	Ivar Janmaat (SURF, Team leader HPC/Research Cloud), Ahmad Hesam (SURF, advisor SURF Research Cloud), Magchiel Bijsterbosch (SURF, Innovation Manager Research), Raymond Oonk (SURF, Program manager)
Version	1.00
Status	Final
Date	22/07/2025

This publication is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International.

Version log

Version	Date	Description
0.5	21/11/2024	First draft version to requesting comments
0.6	11/12/2024	Addressed comments from Ahmad Hesam (SURF) Added sections on EOSC Federation Federating Capabilities, Connecting to EOSC Federation Federating Capabilities, Recommendations and Conclusions
0.7	08/01/2025	Addressed comments from Ahmad Hesam and Ivar Janmaat (SURF) on the sections added in v0.6.
0.8	29/04/2025	Changed title from <i>Comparing SURF Research Cloud with EOSC EU Node</i> to <i>Comparing the SURF pilot node with the EOSC EU Node</i> Addressed comments from Magchiel Bijsterbosch (SURF) Added a section on <i>Organising the National Node</i> Different updates related to the official release of the first EOSC Federation Handbook Added a section on the EOSC Node Architecture. Changing the narrative from SURF Research Cloud to the planned SURF pilot node in mind
0.9	03/06/2025	Addressed comments Maarten Hoogerwerf (SURF), Raymond Oonk (SURF), Ahmad Hesam (SURF)
0.95	22/07/2025	Final draft, addressed final comments from Maarten Hoogerwerf (SURF), Raymond Oonk (SURF)
1.00	22/07/2025	Final version

Table of contents

1. Introduction	3
2. Organising the National Node	3
3. EOSC Federation	4
3.1. EOSC Node architecture	5
3.2. EOSC Federating Capabilities	7
4. EOSC EU Node	8
5. SURF Research Cloud	14
6. Comparing the SURF pilot node with the EOSC EU Node capabilities	20
6.1. Comparing with EOSC EU Node platform capabilities	20
6.2. Comparing with EOSC EU Node Tier-1 services	22
6.3. Connecting to the EOSC Federating Capabilities	25
7. Recommendations	27
8. Conclusions	30

1. Introduction

In February 2023 a report¹ was published in which the alignment of HOSA (Higher Education Sector Architecture) in the Netherlands with EOSC (European Open Science Cloud) was analysed on the level of principles, stakeholders, governance, platform architecture, platform core components and services offered through the platform. This analysis was done from an architectural point of view. As SURF applied to become a pilot node during the build-up phase of the EOSC Federation, discussions have begun around what constitutes a SURF or National Node, how a Node is logically and/or technically structured, and whether SURF has candidate services or technologies available to build a Node platform. With the launch of the EOSC EU Node at the EOSC Symposium 2024 in Berlin² presenting a concrete implementation of an EOSC Node, it became more clear what a Node could look like. After the launch of the EOSC EU Node and the “Deep dive into the EOSC EU Node” session in which Ivar Janmaat, product owner of the SURF Research Cloud³, gave his view on potential use cases and integrations between SURF Research Cloud and EOSC, it became clear SURF Research Cloud was a potential candidate platform to build up a Node.

Here we analyse the potential of using SURF Research Cloud as a pilot Node during the build-up phase of the EOSC Federation by comparing it with the EOSC EU Node.

2. Organising the National Node

With the launch of the EOSC EU Node the EOSC Tripartite Governance started the build-up of the EOSC Federation. To start the build-up phase the EOSC Tripartite Governance launched a survey in the summer of 2024 to assess the interest of organisations to become a pilot Node and contribute to constructing the EOSC Federation. This was the starting point for SURF to start planning for establishing a National Node.

SURF applied to the survey to become a pilot node. After a selection procedure, SURF was selected as one of the first wave pilot Nodes to participate in the build-up phase of the EOSC Federation⁴. Next to the EOSC EU Node and SURF, twelve other candidates have been selected in the first wave of nodes. The EOSC EU Node is depicted as the first node of the EOSC Federation and is seen as the exemplar node for other nodes.

Building up a National Node goes beyond the technical developments to develop and operate a node platform. To position a node as a National Node you need to engage with other stakeholders to organise and scope the node within the National context and how this relates to other National, thematic and institutional initiatives and the EOSC Federation. SURF, as the EOSC Mandated Organisation of the Netherlands, established a National working group consisting of representatives from DANS⁵, eScience Center⁶, SURF, Open Science NL⁷, Health-RI⁸ and the Technical Digital Competence Centres⁹. To discuss the topic of one or more National Nodes the National working group is using the Global Open Research Commons (GORC)¹⁰ model. The GORC model is an

¹ van de Sanden, M. (2023). Aligning the HOSA with EOSC. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7634675>

² <https://eosc.eu/symposium2024>

³ <https://www.surf.nl/en/services/surf-research-cloud>

⁴ <https://eosc.eu/news/2025/02/eoscs-build-up-phase-to-begin-with-march-kick-off/>

⁵ <https://dans.knaw.nl>

⁶ <https://www.esciencecenter.nl/>

⁷ <https://www.openscience.nl/>

⁸ <https://www.health-ri.nl/>

⁹ <https://tdcc.nl/>

¹⁰ Woodford, C., Treloar, A., Leggott, M., Payne, K., Jones, S., Lopez Albacete, J., Madalli, D., Genova, F., Dharmawardena, K., Chibhira, N., Åkerström, W. N., Macneil, R., Nurnberger, A., Pfeiffenberger, H., Tanifuji, M., Zhang, Q., Jones, N., Sesink, L., Wood-Charlson, E., & RDA GORC International Model WG. (2023). The Global Open Research Commons International Model, Version 1 (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00099>

international model and has been developed by the Research Data Alliance¹¹ GORC International Model WG¹². The GORC model is used in this work to map National stakeholders on the essential elements of the GORC model, see figure 1.

Fig 1. Mapping of National stakeholders on the essential elements of the GORC model

This document makes a technical comparison between the EOSC EU Node and the SURF pilot node as planned in the build-up phase. It is therefore focussing on the blue elements of the GORC model and will not address the white elements. It makes a comparison of SURF Research Cloud with the EOSC EU Node as a candidate platform for building the SURF pilot node. It identifies candidate services (initially focusing on SURF services) as Node Core Capabilities to be federated with the EOSC Federating Capabilities and candidate services comparable with the services procured by the European Commission and offered through the EOSC EU Node.

3. EOSC Federation

EOSC has always been depicted as a federation in a System-of-Systems¹³ approach. With the launch of the EOSC Procurement, the EOSC was defined as a Federation of Nodes, the EOSC Federation. The high-level diagram as shown in Figure 2 is also the diagram used in the procurement documentation to explain the EOSC Federation and Node concept. Following this concept the EOSC Federation consists of Nodes acting on a European, Regional, National and/or at a Thematic level making institutional, National, Regional, European and/or Thematic resources available.

¹¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/>

¹² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/gorc-international-model-wg/>

¹³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/System_of_systems

Fig. 2 Diagram as used in the EOSC Procurement documents to describe the EOSC Federation

After finalising the procurement, the European Commission and the contractors started with enabling the EOSC Node and the EOSC Association (EOSC-A) started the writing of the EOSC Federation Handbook¹⁴. The EOSC EU Node was launched during the EOSC Symposium 2024 in Berlin. At the time of this writing the first version of the EOSC Federation Handbook¹⁵ has been published on the 27th of March on Zenodo. The EOSC Federation Handbook will be updated during the build-up phase of the EOSC Federation.

3.1. EOSC Node architecture

Section 4.2 of the EOSC Federation Handbook provides a high-level description of the EOSC Node architecture and the Node Core Capabilities. Figure 3 is a high-level architecture diagram of an EOSC Node, identifying the main elements of an EOSC Node.

¹⁴ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-federation-handbook/>

¹⁵ EOSC Association. (2025). EOSC Federation Handbook. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14999577>

Fig 3. EOSC Node Architecture

The EOSC Federation Handbook defines the main elements as following:

- **Node Core capabilities** that enable the operations of the Node (e.g. AAI, Helpdesk, Monitoring, etc.).
- **Node Resources**: services, data and other research products, usually listed in a catalogue, that end-users of this Node can access directly. These are split into three categories:
 - **Node Generic Capabilities**: employed in the vast majority of scientific disciplines (and therefore relevant to all EOSC Nodes) to perform everyday tasks related to research data management (e.g. a data transfer service or a cloud infrastructure).
 - **Node Research Resources**: domain specific services, datasets and other research products ready-to-use only for researchers of the Node (e.g. domain-specific datasets or an application to process thematic datasets). See Chapter 5 of the EOSC Federation Handbook for a description of Research Resources to be provided by EOSC Nodes.
 - **Node Exchange**: subsets of the generic capabilities and Research Resources a Node makes available to the EOSC Federation. They contribute to the collective EOSC Exchange.
- **Services enabling or participating in Federating Capabilities**

As described in section 4.2.1 of the EOSC Federation Handbook, the Node Core capabilities enable the basic operation of an EOSC Node and a reference implementation of the Node Core Capabilities have been implemented by the EOSC EU Node. Table 1 describes the Node Core Capabilities as defined in the EOSC Federation Handbook.

Table 1: Node Core Capabilities as defined in the EOSC Federation Handbook

Node Core Capabilities	Description
Resource Catalogue and Registry services	Catalogue of resources that can be accessed through the EOSC Node with a search engine to discover, access and order them
AAI	AAI (AARC Blueprint- compliant) enabling access to Node resources (Core and Exchange) via federated credentials (i.e. community AAI and Infrastructure Proxy)

<i>Helpdesk</i>	<i>Support incident response and service requests for services and other integrated resources</i>
<i>Service Monitoring</i>	<i>Monitor the availability and quality of the Node services</i>
<i>Service and Research Product Accounting</i>	<i>Track and record usage of resources</i>
<i>Order Management</i>	<i>A framework for providers to define offers and a unique interface for end-users to request access to resources</i>
<i>Configuration Management System</i>	<i>Shared space to store information on Node capabilities and on how services are provided through the node to ensure consistent service delivery (only for internal use)</i>
<i>User space</i>	<i>Dynamic customisable dashboard, where the node user logs-in, offering easy access to the Node resources.</i>
<i>Application Workflow Management</i>	<i>Orchestrate services, datasets and other research objects on the underlying Node provisioned infrastructure</i>
<i>Resource provisioning</i>	<i>Support users on identifying all available resources for a project and then assigning them to the project</i>

3.2. EOSC Federating Capabilities

An important element of building up the EOSC Federation is to define the federating capabilities for which the Federation is being established, as, the eduroam federation has been established to allow simple, easy, secure wifi connectivity across academic and research institutions across the globe. The EOSC Federation Handbook has defined the EOSC Federating Capabilities as:

EOSC Federating Capabilities are the added-value capabilities offered by the EOSC Federation that allow all EOSC end-users and providers to exploit services, data and other resources in the Federation.

As described on the EOSC Association website¹⁶: *the ambition of the European Open Science Cloud, known as EOSC, is to develop a 'Web of FAIR Data and Services' for science in Europe.* To accomplish this ambition the EOSC Federation is established and the federating capabilities support the aim to enable the *Web of FAIR data and Services*. Therefore, the federating capabilities play a crucial role for the Nodes joining the federation. It is expected that the Federating Capabilities will evolve. Therefore, as described in the EOSC Federation handbook the EOSC Federation will start with an initial set based on earlier activities¹⁷:

The EOSC Federation will begin operating with an initial set of Federating Capabilities identified by the EOSC Forum as key to enable the sharing, discovery, access, and composition of services and research products that cater to the diverse needs of researchers and scientists. These capabilities, listed in Table 4.3, currently enabled by the EOSC EU Node, will be implemented by other EOSC Nodes.

Table 2: Federating Capabilities enabled by the EOSC EU Node as defined in the EOSC Federation Handbook

Federating Capability	Description	Classification
<i>Resource Catalogues and Registry services</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Federated EOSC Resource Catalogue making the Node exchange resources discoverable ● Search engine over the whole EOSC Federation ● Interfaces to allow EOSC Nodes to publish (push) and 	<i>Mandatory</i>

¹⁶ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-about/>

¹⁷ section 4.3.1 Phase 1 for the Federating Capabilities of the EOSC Federation of the EOSC Federation Handbook

Federating Capability	Description	Classification
	<i>retrieve (pull) resources to/from the federated catalogue</i>	
AAI	<i>Allows users to log in with their own institute credentials (eduGAIN) to access EOSC resources</i>	<i>Recommended¹⁸</i>
Application Workflow Management	<i>Orchestrate services, datasets and other research objects on multiple federated nodes</i>	<i>Recommended</i>
Service Monitoring	<i>Provide information about the availability and quality of EOSC services (Core and Exchange)</i>	<i>Recommended</i>
Service and Research Product Accounting	<i>Provide information about usage of services and resources in EOSC (Core and Exchange)</i>	<i>Recommended</i>
Order Management	<i>Offer a framework for providers to define offers and a unique interface for end-users to request access to resources</i>	<i>Recommended</i>
Helpdesk	<i>Federation of Integrated Helpdesks</i>	<i>Recommended</i>
Management System	<i>FitSM-based Service Management System (SMS) that can be federated with SMS from other EOSC Nodes. This includes Security Coordination between Nodes too.</i>	<i>Recommended</i>

Candidate nodes planning to join the EOSC Federation need at least to connect to the mandatory federating capabilities during the build-up phase.

4. EOSC EU Node

The EOSC EU Node is the first node of the EOSC Federation procured by the European Commission and is hosted and operated by third-party contractors¹⁹. As described on the EOSC EU Node website²⁰:

EOSC EU Node is a platform that primarily supports multi-disciplinary and multi-national research promoting the use of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data and supplementary services in Europe and beyond. Within this environment, researchers can find easy-to-use tools and the much-needed support to both individually and collectively, plan, execute, disseminate, and assess their typical research workflows and outcomes across the EOSC ecosystem.

In addition, EOSC EU Node is a platform that facilitates the creation of the EOSC Federation, following the system of systems architectural principle of federated research infrastructures. It aims to provide a technical and administrative blueprint and interoperability framework for other potential infrastructure node candidates to be established. EOSC EU Node can be recognised as the first European-level node of the EOSC Federation promoted by the European Commission as an operationalised platform in production.

Figure 4 is a screenshot of the EOSC EU Node. It provides an overview of the EOSC EU Node with information for researchers and contributors, a search bar to discover research outputs, the offered services (i.e. File Sync & Share, Interactive Notebooks, Large File Transfers, Virtual machines, Cloud Container Platform, Bulk Data Transfer), updates from the EOSC Community and Events. At the top of the website, the EOSC EU Node provides a menu bar with:

¹⁸ Although joining the AAI Federation to enable the single sign-on over the federated nodes is only recommended, each node should enable access to its services and other resources via eduGain IdPs (see Section 4.5).

¹⁹ <https://eosc.eu/news/2023/11/european-commission-announces-results-of-the-eosc-procurement/>

²⁰ <https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/about/eosc-eu-node>

- Service descriptions of the offered Services,
- Resource Hub for the discovery of resources (i.e. publications, data, software, services, data sources, training, interoperability guidelines, tools and other products),
- Support through the EOSC EU Node Helpdesk, Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ), User Guides and Documentation of the offered services and a link to training material provisioned through an external platform²¹,
- Information for Contributors (e.g. general information, a categorisation of contributors, core capabilities potentially offered by the EOSC EU Node),
- Information on News and Events,
- And to a personal User Space which requires a user to login.

Fig. 4 Portal of the EOSC EU Node

After logging in a user comes in his/her personal user space with access to the offered Services (i.e. File Sync & Share, Interactive Notebooks, Large File Transfer, Cloud Container Platform, Virtual Machines, Bulk Data Transfer and Other services if available), General capabilities (i.e. Group information, Orders, Credits, Favourites, Settings) and Quick links (i.e. Helpdesk, Resource Hub, Monitoring and Training Platform), see figure 5.

²¹ <https://openplato.eu/blocks/catalog/list.php?searchurl=1&categories=164>

Fig. 5 User Space of the EOSC EU Node

The User Space of the EOSC EU Node enables the following capabilities, see Table 3.

Table 3 EOSC EU Node User Space capabilities

Capability	Description
User Space	
Overview (sidebar)	Provides access to the User Space login page which provides an overview and access to the procured Tier1 services
Notifications (sidebar)	Notifications is the prime communication channel of the EOSC EU Node to communicate messages to the users.
Tools Hub (sidebar)	The Tools Hub provides an overview of the tools (e.g. Virtual Clusters, VMs, Containers, Notebooks) made available by researchers on the EOSC EU Node.
Services (sidebar)	Through the Services sidebar section, users have easy access to procured Tier 1 services offered through the EOSC EU Node: File Sync and Share, Interactive Notebooks, large file transfer, Cloud Container Platform, Virtual Machines, Bulk Data Transfer, and Other Services.
General (sidebar)	Through the General sidebar section, users have easy access to group information, orders, credits, favourites and personal profile Settings.
Quicklinks (sidebar)	Through the Quick Links sidebar section, users have easy access to: the Helpdesk, Resource Hub, Monitoring and Training Platform.

Capability	Description
User Space window (Centre Window)	The centre window is the main User Space window which enables all functionalities of the EOSC EU Node.
Identity Management	Users need to log in to get access to the User Space. The User Space provides a Single Sign-On (SSO) environment that allows users to log in to the EOSC EU Node services, as far as capable, in a transparent way with one set of credentials. The login and SSO environment is based on the GEANT MyAccessID service ²² .
User Access Policies	<p>The EOSC EU Node User Access Policy²³ ("UAP") defines the access groups, their corresponding access rights, service limits, and virtual credit allocation policies for the users of the EOSC EU Node's Resources ("Resources") and Services ("Services") as granted by the European, Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology, Unit C.1 High-Performance Computing and Applications (hereinafter referred to as "Operating Unit"). This policy ensures users have the appropriate level of access according to their role and affiliation while maintaining system integrity, security, and compliance with EU regulations and applicable law.</p> <p>The EOSC EU Node User Access Policy recognizes 3 Access Groups:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Access Group AP-0 (Public View): Access Group AP-0 includes all users who are not authenticated (i.e., not logged in). This group is granted open access to publicly available content on the Websites. ● Access Group AP-A1 (Institutional View): includes users authenticated via eduGAIN inter-federation and EU Login, with specific restrictions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ eduGAIN: IdPs restricted to EU275 and Horizon Europe Associated Countries, filtered for affiliation attributes of employee and staff (i.e., faculty, students, affiliates, members, alums and library-walk-in are excluded from this group). ○ EU Login: Restricted to European Commission and its agencies staff, filtered by domain attribute (i.e., citizen scientists authenticated via eIDAS are excluded). ● Access Group AP-B (Researcher View): includes users authenticated via eduGAIN inter-federation, with the following restrictions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ eduGAIN: IdPs restricted to EU27 and Horizon Europe Associated Countries, filtered for affiliation attributes of faculty only (i.e., expected attribute of academic researchers).
Services	Through the Services sidebar section, users have easy access to procured Tier 1 services offered through the EOSC EU Node.
File Sync & Share	Provides access to an Owncloud ²⁴ -based file sync and share service which can be accessed via a web browser, desktop and mobile app. The File Sync & Share service can automatically sync files to interactive notebooks. In the User Space window, a user has basic access to manage his/her data in the File Sync & Share service. Also, a link ²⁵ is provided to the full Owncloud service and user interface including access to a file editor.

²² <https://ds.myaccessid.org/ds/>

²³ <https://www.eosc.athenarc.gr/system/files?file=2024-10/EOSC-EU-Node-User-Access-Policy-v1.0.pdf>

²⁴ <https://owncloud.com/>

²⁵ <https://drive.open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu>

Capability	Description
Interactive Notebooks	The Interactive Notebooks service is a managed instance of JupyterHub, backed by major resource providers and operated in a multi-zone setup for better availability. A typical user will connect to the Web interface of the Hub, select a resource size they want to work with and open an integrated Jupyter environment in their browser. In the User Space window, a user can request access to an Interactive Notebook environment. A user can request a small, medium and/or large environment. A user has insight into the credit costs of these environments.
Large File Transfer ²⁶	The Large File Transfer service is based on Filesender ²⁷ and is a service to streamline large file transfers online with added security and integrity. Users can control file access and retention periods, ensuring files are accessible only to intended recipients and for a specified duration. Notifications are sent both to senders and recipients, confirming file uploads and downloads. The Large File Transfer allows the sharing of files up to 1TB. A user has insight into the credit costs of these environments.
Cloud Container Platform	The Cloud Container Platform, built on OKD and Kubernetes, offers a robust environment for deploying and managing containerised applications. Users can use Docker and OCI-compliant containers to automate tasks like load balancing, service discovery, and pod scaling, ensuring efficient resource use. The platform supports dynamic storage provisioning and integrates seamlessly with CI/CD pipelines to enhance your development workflows. In the User Space window, a user can request access to a cloud-native containerized environment to deploy a containerized application. A user can request a small, medium and/or large environment. A user has insight into the credit costs of these environments. The Cloud Container Platform is only available for users with an access policy ²⁸ of AP-B (Researcher View).
Virtual Machines	The Virtual Machines service offers a variety of customizable resources (CPU, memory, storage) across two OpenStack sites that users can allocate to create their own VMs, either through pre-configured templates or fully custom setups. They support high-performance computing, secure data storage, network isolation, and multi-user collaboration. In the User Space window, a user can deploy virtual machines to create isolated environments for conducting experiments, testing different configurations, and ensuring the reproducibility of research by packaging the entire software stack and data dependencies within VM images. A user can request a small, medium and/or large environment and can therefore deploy a simple single node to complete cluster configurations. A user has insight into the credit costs of these environments. The Virtual Machines service is only available for users with an access policy of AP-B (Researcher View).
Bulk Data Transfer ¹³	Bulk Data Transfer is an extension of computing services provided by the EOSC EU Node. It provides data transfer mechanics that help end-users and projects in handling stage-in and stage-out transfers of large (TB-PB range) datasets to and from compute infrastructure back-ends. The Bulk Data Transfer service is based on the FTS3 ²⁹ service and supports data transfers

²⁶ The *Large File Transfer* and the *Bulk Data Transfer* service are two independent services which are not directly related to each other.

²⁷ <https://filesender.org/>

²⁸ <https://www.eosc.athenarc.gr/system/files?file=2024-10/EOSC-EU-Node-User-Access-Policy-v1.0.pdf>

²⁹ <https://fts3-docs.web.cern.ch/fts3-docs/>

Capability	Description
	via the GridFTP protocol ³⁰ . The Bulk Data Transfer service is only accessible to users with an access policy of AP-B (Researcher View).
... Other Services	Provides an overview of Services onboarded into the EOSC EU Node or provided by the EOSC Federation Nodes. At the time of this writing, 0 Other Services are listed.
General	Through the General sidebar section, users have easy access to group information, orders, credits, favourites and personal profile Settings.
Groups	Groups aim to facilitate collaborative work by sharing access to EOSC EU Node resources. A Group can be created only by a user with access policy AP-B level (Researcher view). An AP-B level user (Group Owner) can create at most two (2) Groups. Any authenticated user (access policy of AP-A and above) can be invited as a Group Member. Group Members inherit the Access Rights to existing Services and Resources of the Group Owner. A user cannot be a member of more than four (4) groups.
Orders	Users of the EOSC EU Node can view and manage all your orders made through the EOSC EU node. For each order, the user can see the ID of the order, the ordered service, the project type, the last activity within the order and the status. A user can click on the ordered service and see some more detailed information.
Credits	<p>Credits are the virtual currency within the EOSC EU Node which can be used to spend to consume select services according to a user's needs. Credits have no monetary value and are used exclusively in the EOSC EU Node to allow fair, transparent, and equal access to its services across the entire European research community. Credits are provided to you for free of charge (at the point of use) by the European Commission the first time you log in and are automatically renewed every three months. The amount of credits a user receives depends on the level of access to various services and is set automatically based on the affiliation information shared by your home organisation.</p> <p>Access Groups and Access Rights:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Access Group AP-B (Researcher View): 500 credits ● Access Group AP-A (Insider View): 100 credits ● Access Group AP-0 (Public View): 0 credits <p>More detailed information can be found in the EOSC EU Node User Access Policy³¹.</p>
Favourites	A user can mark any resource (e.g. Publication, Data, Software, Service, Data Source, Training, Interoperability Guideline, or other products) in the Resource Hub as a favourite. Favourites in the User Space provides easy access to all the resources a user has marked as a favourite in the Resource Hub.
Settings	Provides an overview of the User profile and allows a user to set 1 or more Scientific Domains.

³⁰ <https://gridcf.org/gct-docs/latest/gridftp/index.html>

³¹ <https://www.eosc.athenarc.gr/system/files?file=2024-10/EOSC-EU-Node-User-Access-Policy-v1.0.pdf>

Capability	Description
Quicklinks	Through the quick links, a user has easy access to: the Helpdesk, Resource Hub, Monitoring and the Training Platform.
Helpdesk	The Helpdesk quick link opens the Helpdesk form to request assistance in troubleshooting or seeking guidance. The EOSC EU Node has a support team to support the users of the EOSC EU Node.
Resource Hub	The Resource Hub is the discovery portal of the EOSC EU Node to discover resources. At the time of this writing the Resource Hub makes 128M publications, data, software, services, data sources, training, interoperability guidelines, tools and other products discoverable and accessible. The Resource Hub is based on the OpenAIRE Knowledge Graph ³² , extended with resources from the European Open Data Portal ³³ and Software Heritage ³⁴ . Users can filter resources based on Access Rights, Scientific Domain, Document Type and/or Horizontal service. Basic information is provided for each of the resources.
Monitoring	The Monitoring page provides monitoring information on the EOSC EU Node Core (i.e. Training Platform, Resource Hub, Web Front Office, User Space, Tools Hub, EOSC AAI, Helpdesk and Security Tools) and Exchange services (i.e. Bulk Data Transfer, File Sync & Share, Interactive Notebooks (EU-1 + 2), Large File Transfer, Virtual Machines (EU-1 + 2), Cloud Container Platform (EU-1 +2). Monitoring is based on the ARGO monitoring service ³⁵ from GRNET to measure the availability and reliability of IT infrastructures. ARGO is based on simulating user access. ARGO is also used by EGI and EUDAT for monitoring services.
Training Platform	The Training Platform is a quick link that directs users to the OpenPlato training platform from OpenAIRE. Via the OpenPlato platform users have access to a rich set of courses. At the time of this writing, the OpenPlato platform offers access to 31 courses, which will grow over time. The OpenPlato platform also provides a Dashboard of planned courses and offers a calendar function to plan courses.

5. SURF Research Cloud

SURF Research Cloud is a portal in which researchers can easily build virtual research environments (e.g. workspaces) for a specific research project, and use preconfigured workspaces and datasets. It started as a replacement for the SURF HPC Cloud interface and acts as a middleware layer to enable access to SURF HPC Cloud and other provisioned cloud computing resources. SURF Research Cloud follows the principle of infrastructure-as-code, providing workspaces as human-readable scripts with built-in version control. The configuration script ensures the research environment is deployed exactly as specified. The specified research workspace can consist of IaaS, PaaS or SaaS resources and can contain datasets that can be rebuilt at any time.

SURF Research Cloud provides a catalog of workspace configurations and cloud infrastructure providers that researchers can use. Institutions, research communities and suppliers can contribute to SURF Research Cloud's functionality and catalog by co-developing new workspace configurations and/or become one of the available

³² <https://graph.openaire.eu/>

³³ <https://data.europa.eu/en>

³⁴ <https://www.softwareheritage.org/>

³⁵ <https://grnet.gr/en/services/cloud-services/argo-monitoring-service/>

cloud providers. SURF Research Cloud is, at the time of this writing, integrated with SURF HPC Cloud and with public clouds such as Amazon Web Services, Microsoft Azure and the Oracle Cloud infrastructure .

When a researcher visits the SURF Research Cloud portal³⁶, they see a welcome page, see figure 6, with basic information and a link to user documentation describing the service: how to get access, how to configure workspaces, which computing platforms are available, how to use external storage and datasets, how to collaborate in collaborative groups and with fellow researchers, and information about budgets, credits and how resources are accounted for. To get access to SURF Research Cloud a researcher needs to be a member of a SURF Research Access Management³⁷ (SRAM) Collaborative Organization (CO) that is coupled with SURF Research Cloud as a service provided via SRAM.

Fig. 6 SURF Research Cloud Portal

After logging in a researcher will see his/her personal dashboard, with an overview of workspaces, profile, wallet information, and options to create resources, see figure 7.

³⁶ <https://portal.live.surfresearchcloud.nl/>

³⁷ SURF Research Access Management is a platform that allows institutions to delegate access management for research services to research collaborations. It enables quick, easy, and secure management of research collaborations. This service is built on established international agreements for authorization and authentication in education and research.

Fig. 7 User Dashboard SURF Research Cloud

The SURF Research Cloud dashboard enables the following capabilities, see Table 2.

Table 4: SURF Research Cloud Dashboard capabilities

Capability	Description
Dashboard	Is the web user environment of the user after logging into SURF Research Cloud. It provides access to the user: Profile, Wallet, Catalog Items, Help, quick actions to create a new workspace, storage and to request a new wallet, and also an environment to manage (e.g. pause, resume delete) existing workspaces, manage storage spaces, and advanced features to manage IP addresses and networks.
Create new workspace (quick action)	Via the create new workspace quick action a wizard is started to create a new workspace. The wizard consists of selecting an SRAM collaboration under which the workspace will be created, a wallet if multiple wallets are available, to which the workspace is charged, the catalog item, the cloud provider, the size of the VM and the operating system, if available configuring options, providing a personalised name to the workspace and submit the request. Selecting an SRAM collaboration will determine the access scope of the workspace, and who within the collaboration has access and/or can modify the workspace. After submitting the request, the workspace is created and started. Users can monitor this process in the workspace area of the Dashboard.
Create new storage (quick action)	Via the create new storage quick action a workflow is started to create a new storage space. The workflow consists of selecting an SRAM collaboration under which the storage will be created, a wallet, if multiple wallets are available, to which the storage space is charged, selecting a cloud provider, the flavour and size of the storage space, providing a personalised name and description and submitting the request. Selecting an SRAM collaboration will determine the access scope to the storage, and who within the collaboration has access and/or can modify the storage. After submitting the request the storage space is created and can be used within workspaces. Users can monitor this process in the storage area of the

Capability	Description
	Dashboard.
Request new wallet (quick action)	The request new wallet opens a request window via which a user can request a new wallet. The user must provide a short description, specify an existing contract to which the new wallet will belong and can provide additional remarks to support the request. After submitting the request, the owner of the contract will be contacted to validate and approve the new wallet.
Configured/active	Below the quick actions section of the dashboard, different tabs are provided to view workspaces, storage and advanced IP and Network options.
Workspaces (paused/running)	The workspaces tab provides an overview of all configured and/or active workspaces. Users can manage their workspaces, pause, resume and delete workspaces, attach a storage space to a workspace, view a workspace log and/or manage security groups (e.g. firewall settings).
Storage (available/in-use)	The storage tab provides an overview of the configured storage spaces and for each of the storage spaces the status (i.e. available, in-use). Attaching and/or detaching a storage space to a workspace is managed in a workspace, see row above. In the storage tab, users can delete available storage spaces.
IP addresses (advanced)	Provides an overview of reserved IP addresses. A reserved IP address is accessible from anywhere on the internet. However, by default catalog items have only open ports for SSH (22), RDP (3389), HTTP (80) and HTTPS (443) access to a workspace. SRAM collaboration members with the role <i>src_co_developer</i> can configure through the security groups tab of configured/running workspaces the network traffic rules of a workspace. These can be configured dynamically during the lifetime of a workspace. Members of a workspace who do not have a developer role need to ask a member with a developer role to change the security group's rules. Support for modifying network rules needs to be requested through the helpdesk https://servicedesk.surfsara.nl .
Networks (advanced)	If a user runs multiple workspaces a private network can be created to communicate safely between the workspaces. An overview of the configured private networks is provided in this view.
Identity Management	To get access to the Dashboard users need to log in. Authentication and SSO is based on SRAM. SRAM is used for identity and group management. It uses eduGAIN for identity management and EduTeams for group management. Preferably, groups are created within the institute organisation and not in the SURF organisation.
User Access Policies	A user needs to be a member of an SRAM Collaboration that is tied to the SURF Research Cloud.
Profile (menu)	Via the Profile tab a user has easy access to his/her profile information, collaboration organisations and to request a new collaboration organisation. User profiles are centrally managed in SRAM.

Capability	Description
Request a collaboration at SURF (quick action)	<p>A collaboration³⁸ is an ad-hoc group of people who are allowed to work together by sharing resources. A researcher can easily request a collaboration and invite other researchers to collaborate. Collaboration organisations are self-organised to distribute tasks, including administering the collaboration.</p> <p>If an institution cannot create a collaboration for a researcher, a researcher can request one with SURF. When requesting a new collaboration a request window and a user can specify a new collaboration name. The request is forwarded to the service desk to create the new collaboration in SURF's SRAM organization.</p>
Profile (user)	The user profile provides access to basic user information (e.g. username and email address), public SSH keys, and API tokens via which programmatic access can be provided to SURF Research Cloud. The public SSH keys and application tokens are managed through SRAM. Through the API tokens tab of the user profile, Researchers can request an API token to interact programmatically with SURF Research Cloud.
Collaborative organisations	In this section, the user has an overview of the collaborative organizations (CO) of which the user is a member. The memberships within a CO are managed through SRAM.
Collaboration (member of)	For each of the collaborations, a user can view the members, groups and secrets of the collaboration and can manage connections to external storage services: ResearchDrive ³⁹ and/or a WebDav-enabled storage service.
Wallet (menu)	Via the Wallet menu tab, a user has access to his/her available wallets and an easy way to request a new wallet. Wallets are the means through which workspace resources are budgeted and resource usage accounted for. A wallet is backed by a contract, which can be financed via an NWO grant ⁴⁰ or a Research Capacity Computing Service (RCCS) pay-per-use contract ⁴¹ . Wallet information is managed within the SURF Research Cloud.
Credits	Resource usage within SURF Research Cloud is budgeted and is accounted for in credits. When configuring a new workspace users are informed about the usage costs (e.g. credits/day) of the VM configuration options.
Personal wallets	While a contract can be entitled to a group of people, a wallet is by default personal. Personal wallets draw credits from the pool assigned to the contract. The contract owner is responsible for setting a maximum limit to personal wallets.
Project wallets	Project wallets are project-wide wallets for collaborations as managed in SRAM and credits assigned to a project wallet are shared by all members within the collaboration.
Request a new wallet (quick action)	Via a quick action, a user can request a new wallet. When a user requests a wallet through quick action, managers of the SURF Research Cloud always contact the contract owner to validate and approve the new wallet.

³⁸ A collaboration, in the context of SRC and SRAM, is a means to manage access to research services and applications

³⁹ <https://researchdrive.surfsara.nl/index.php/login>

⁴⁰ <https://www.surf.nl/en/services/surf-research-cloud>

⁴¹ <https://www.surf.nl/en/research-capacity-computing-service>

Capability	Description
Your wallets	Provides an overview of the user-available wallets. A user can have access to multiple wallets via which resources in SURF Research Cloud are accounted for.
Catalog (menu)	The Catalog menu tab provides direct access to the Catalog and options for users to view, add and manage Components and Catalog items.
Catalog	Provides an overview of the available catalog items and accessible datasets. A user can view detailed information about each catalog item: basic details such as description, documentation, and support information, advanced details such as catalog item components, cloud settings as operating systems, port configurations and overwritable parameters. This helps users with selecting a catalog item to configure a workspace.
Components	Provides an overview of available components on SURF Research Cloud. A component is one script (typically an Ansible Playbook) that realizes a particular feature in a workspace. This feature might be OS-related, like an alternative login method. Or a component might, for instance, install a particular software package. Users with a <i>developer</i> role have the option to add and develop their components and make them publicly available or keep them closed to a particular collaboration. At the time of this writing, SURF Research Cloud contained 159 components.
Catalog items	Provides an overview of all catalog items available on SURF Research Cloud, including disabled catalog items. Catalog items are templates that can be started and result in a workspace - an actual resource that can be logged into and that can be used. Users with a <i>developer</i> role have the option to add and build their catalog item based on the available components and make it publicly available or keep them closed to a particular collaboration. SURF Research Cloud contained 76 catalog items at the time of this writing.
Help (menu tab)	Via the Help menu tab, users have access to documentation, an option to request support and system status monitoring.
Documentation	Provides a link to the SURF Research Cloud user documentation maintained on the SURF Servicedesk wiki environment. It provides detailed information on how to get access, how to create and manage workspaces, storage, and datasets, how to manage budgets, work together in collaboration organisations and how to create new components and catalog items.
Request support	Users of SURF Research Cloud can request support. A simple help message box is provided in which a user can ask his/her question. The help request message is registered with the relevant metadata (such as user ID, workspace ID, etc) in the SURF service desk. Optionally the first line support can be delegated to Digital Competence Centers (DCC) of member institutes.
System status	On the Help page, users can find the detailed status of the services enabled and on the workspace, user, catalog, wallet and contact request components. There are also indicators of the availability of resources that are in high demand (GPUs, high-mem nodes)

6. Comparing the SURF pilot node with the EOSC EU Node capabilities

While SURF Research Cloud can act as a good basis to build up a National Node, it has not been developed as a generic EOSC node platform, but as an overlay platform to enable easy access to cloud computing resources from different providers. For SURF Research Cloud to become a node platform capable of joining the EOSC Federation, SURF Research Cloud needs to be extended with other SURF services as depicted in figure 8 and connected to the EOSC Federating Capabilities, see section 3.2.

Fig 8. High-level view of the planned SURF pilot node

A more detailed comparison will be made in the next sections.

6.1. Comparing with EOSC EU Node platform capabilities

After providing an overview of the capabilities of the EOSC EU Node and SURF Research Cloud in chapters 4 and 5, Table 5 provides a mapping of the SURF Research Cloud capabilities on top of the EOSC EU Node capabilities. The first column 1 of Table # lists generic capabilities for mapping the EOSC EU Node and SURF Research Cloud capabilities. Columns 2 and 3 describe how the capability has been implemented in the EOSC EU Node and SURF Research Cloud. Column 4 provides a comment and/or a recommendation to further align the SURF Research Cloud capability with the EOSC EU Node capability.

Table 5: Mapping of the SURF Research Cloud capabilities on the EOSC EU Node capabilities

Capability	EOSC EU Node	National pilot node	Comment
Website	Web Front Office, see https://open-science-cloud.europa.eu .	Website of SURF Research Cloud, see https://portal.live.surfresearchcloud.nl .	
User space	EOSC EU Node User Space requires users to login	SRC Dashboard requires users to login	

Capability	EOSC EU Node	National pilot node	Comment
Identity Management	GEANT MyAccessID	SURF SRAM and SURFconext	SRAM makes use of some of the same technologies and principles as MyAccessID.
Group Management	EOSC EU Node Group management	SRAM Collaborative Organizations	Not sure if the groups created through the EOSC EU Node web interface are managed in MyAccessID.
Resource catalogue	OpenAIRE RDGraph extended with data portals from the European Commission.	Not available	SRC does not have a public discovery portal for research products, services, and/or the catalog items made available in SRC. A Dutch discovery portal ⁴² has been developed based on OpenAIRE. A potential development could be to integrate the Dutch discovery portal in the SRC public web interface, not enclosed behind the login. The discovery portal can be extended with a service catalogue providing an overview of services supporting research available in the Netherlands.
Tools catalog	EOSC EU Node Tools Hub	SRC Dashboard Catalog	
Application Workflow Management (AWM)	EGI Compute Orchestration services	Not available	SRC does not have an automatic scale-out capability but has been integrated with different commercial cloud providers (AWS, Azure, Oracle). A potential extension is to implement and/or integrate with a workload and infrastructure manager to allow automatic scale-out to other cloud providers. Possible options are on the roadmap, like ELIXIR ⁴³

⁴² <https://netherlands.openaire.eu/>

⁴³ <https://elixir-europe.org/>

Capability	EOSC EU Node	National pilot node	Comment
			TeSS ⁴⁴ /WES ⁴⁵ , the SLURM ⁴⁶ API to connect to Snellius, Spider or for scheduling jobs on the Kubernetes clusters from EGI. Another option is to integrate with the AWM from the EOSC EU Node.
Monitoring	GRNET ARGO Monitoring service	SRC System status on the Dashboard Help tab	The SRC monitoring seems to focus more on technical service components rather than on real user behavior patterns, as seen in the monitoring of EOSC EU Node components.
Accounting	EOSC EU Node credit system	SRC Wallet and credit system	The EOSC EU node and SRC both make use of a system-specific credit system. The credit systems allow budgeting and accounting resources. An EOSC Federation credit system could be an interesting idea to budget and account resources across Nodes within the Federation.
Helpdesk	Zammad instance hosted at KIT.	SURF ServiceDesk based on JIRA	Depending on the policies of the EOSC Federation the SURF Service Desk should be connected with the EOSC Federation Helpdesk federating capability.
Service Management System	EGI FitSM processes	SRC Service management	Needs to be compliant with the EOSC Federation Policies.

6.2. Comparing with EOSC EU Node Tier-1 services

Table 4 provides an overview of the EOSC EU Node Tier-1 services which have been procured through the EOSC Procurement Lot 2 and 3. These Tier-1 services have been seamlessly integrated within the EOSC EU Node platform. Table 6 makes a comparison between the EOSC EU Node Tier-1 services with services and capabilities offered as planned through SURF pilot node. In the Comments column, potential options are provided to align National pilot node and/or SURF services and capabilities further with the EOSC EU Node Tier-1 services.

⁴⁴ <https://tess.elixir-europe.org>

⁴⁵ <https://github.com/elixir-cloud-aa/cwl-WES>

⁴⁶ <https://slurm.schedmd.com/>

Table 6: Comparison of the EOSC EU Node Tier-1 services with SURF candidate services

EOSC EU Node Tier-1 Services		SURF pilot node	Comments
File Sync and Share (EFSS)	Based on Owncloud	Research Drive based on Owncloud	Owncloud has been integrated within the EOSC EU Node User Space. To improve the user experience for researchers, a potential improvement is to integrate Research Drive in the SRC Dashboard Interface similar to the EOSC EU Node.
Interactive Notebooks	Based on Jupyter Hub and hosted at 2 provider sites	Jupyter notebook templates are provisioned through the SRC Catalog and can be run on the SRC Cloud resources	In the EOSC EU Node, the Interactive Notebooks are provisioned through dedicated JupyterHub resources hosted at 2 sites while in SURF Research Cloud the Interactive Notebooks (Jupyter Notebooks) are run in VMs. In the context of this report, this is considered an implementation detail.
Virtual Machines	Based on OpenStack and hosted at 2 provider sites. EOSC EU Node makes use of TOSCA templates.	Virtual Machines templates are provisioned through the SRC Catalog and can be run on the SRC Cloud resources. SRC makes use of Terraform and Ansible templates.	To make SRC and the EOSC EU Node Virtual Machines component compatible/interoperable and allow the movement of VMs between SRC and EOSC EU Node and visa-versa, SRC could assess aligning the middleware templates with the EOSC EU Node, by e.g. adopting TOSCA.
Container Platform	Based on OKD Kubernetes and hosted at 2 provider sites	Based on Docker containers	In the EOSC EU Node, containers are provisioned through dedicated Container Platform resources hosted at 2 sites while in SURF Research Cloud containers are run on cloud resources. In the context of this report, this is considered an implementation detail.

EOSC EU Node Tier-1 Services		SURF pilot node	Comments
Bulk Data Transfers	Based on FTS3 and hosted by CERN.	An FTS3 service is available for any community to use ⁴⁷ , but it is not advertised as such.	The plan is to integrate SRC with the SURF Yoda Hosting service for moving files while still managing them. Optionally, SURF could advertise the local FTS3 service as a Bulk Data Transfer service or alternatively integrate SRC with the Bulk Data Transfer service offered through the EOSC EU Node.
Large File Transfer	Based on GEANT Filesender.	SURF offers SURFfilesender which provides in principle the same functionality but has not been integrated with SRC.	SURFfilesender can optionally be integrated with SRC.
Access Policy	The EOSC EU Node introduced an access policy for EOSC EU Node Exchange Services that is based on a credit system, a virtual currency of the EOSC EU Node, which expresses the relative (and actual) cost of services but has no real monetary value. Users are already familiar with the pay-as-you-go model from commercial offerings. Users know in advance the cost/credits of the use of a service. Users are allocated free credits. The amount of free credits depends on the access policy of a user (i.e. AP level B - eduGAIN faculty, AP level A1 - eduGAIN employee or staff, AP level A - other with view-only access) and the credits are replenished every 3 months. Scarce and/or high-demand services need to be requested via the Helpdesk.	Access Policy is defined based on NWO grants (small and big grants), RCCS and/or project-based contracts. The budget is managed through a wallet and an amount of credits associated with the grant and/or contract.	
Other services	Catalogue of Tier 2 services	Commercial clouds (e.g. Amazon AWS, Microsoft	

⁴⁷ https://doc.grid.surfsara.nl/en/latest/Pages/Advanced/storage_clients/fts.html#surfsara-fts-instance

EOSC EU Node Tier-1 Services		SURF pilot node	Comments
		Azure and Oracle Cloud) which are tightly integrated within SRC.	

6.3. Connecting to the EOSC Federating Capabilities

In section 2 an overview of the initial proposed Federating Capabilities (mandatory or recommended) for a Node to join the EOSC Federation during the build-up phase. If SURF Research Cloud is going to be used as the platform to build up a Node capability to join the EOSC Federation, SURF Research Cloud at least needs to connect to the mandatory Federated Capabilities. For each of the recommended Federating Capabilities the working group governing the Node developments need to assess and decide on which and how SURF Research Cloud, as a Node platform, can and/or will connect to a Federating Capability.

Table 5 provides an overview of the Federating Capabilities and how these can be implemented within SURF Research Cloud.

Table 7: Options for SURF Research Cloud to connect to EOSC Federation Federating Capabilities

Federating Capability	Classification	Description
Resource Catalogues and Registry services	Mandatory	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Through this Federating Capability a Node publishes the services and resources onboarded into the EOSC Federation. SURF Research Cloud does not hold a general resource catalogue and service registry to make services and resources discoverable within the EOSC Federation. The catalog provided in SURF Research Cloud is geared to the VM templates that can be provisioned on the cloud resources offered through SURF Resource Cloud. SURF Services are published on the SURF website⁴⁸. The Node Service and Resource Catalogue need to be compliant with the EOSC Profiles⁴⁹, at least the mandatory fields. To connect to the Resource Catalogue and Service Registry federating capability a Service and Resource Catalogue compliant with the EOSC Profiles can be developed and onboard the services and resources automatically through APIs or onboard the services manually. If SURF Research Cloud is used as a platform for a National Node through which services are on boarded from the Netherlands to the EOSC Federation, local processes and criteria need to be defined to onboard services into the National Node and to the EOSC Federation.
Identity Management	Recommended	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SURF Research Cloud identity management is provided through SRAM. SRAM supports federated logins through SURFconext and through eduGAIN federation. SURF Research Cloud with SRAM is geared to join the identity management federating capability. Providing a full SSO user experience across all services is an area of future developments.
Application Workflow Management	Recommended	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SRC does not have an automatic scale-out capability but has been integrated with different commercial cloud providers (AWS, Azure, Oracle).

⁴⁸ <https://www.surf.nl/en/services>

⁴⁹ <https://eosc-profiles.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

Federating Capability	Classification	Description
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A potential extension is to implement and/or integrate with a workload and infrastructure manager to allow automatic scale-out to other cloud providers. Possible options are on the roadmap, like ELIXIR TeSS/WES, the SLURM API to connect to Snellius, Spider or for scheduling jobs on the Kubernetes clusters from EGI. Another option is to integrate with the AWM from the EOSC EU Node.
Service Monitoring	Recommended	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SURF Research Cloud monitoring looks more based on technical service components and not based on actual user pattern scenarios as in the monitoring of the EOSC EU Node components. • SURF Knowledge Base provides a service status overview⁵⁰ for all services SURF offers for research. This service status overview is a wiki page that is manually maintained by the service teams. • SURF services offered for research are monitored at system and operational level and the status of a service is maintained at SURF Knowledge Base service status wiki page⁵¹. This wiki page is manually maintained by the service teams. • To connect to the monitoring federating capability SURF can develop a central monitoring service compatible with the EOSC Federation monitoring federated capability⁵².
Service Accounting	Recommended	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Budget for SURF Resource Cloud usage is obtained through a NWO Grant or through an RCCS contract. • A contract available to be used on SURF Research Cloud provides a certain amount of credits. • Through the <i>Wallet</i> tab, a user has insight in the usage of SURF Research Cloud resources and available budget. • For NWO Grant and RCCS financial contract reporting SURF Research Cloud usage is registered in the <i>SURF Central Budgeting and Accounting</i> (CBA) service. The CBA service is centrally used for budgeting and accounting of resource usage of all services in NWO Grants and RCCS contracts. • To connect the Service Accounting federating capability the CBA service needs to be made compatible with the service accounting federating capability and need to publish usage numbers for those projects/contracts coming forth through the EOSC Federation.
Order Management	Recommended	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SURF Research Cloud does not manage the ordering of services and resources. These are managed through SURF customer support. • To connect to the Order Management federating capability SURF customer support services and processes need to be aligned with the Order Management process adopted within the EOSC Federation.
Helpdesk	Recommended	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SURF Resource Cloud Helpdesk is based on a web form that sends an email to the SURF Servicedesk⁵³ to register a ticket. • To connect SURF Research Cloud Helpdesk to the Helpdesk federating capability, it is not that the Helpdesk form used on SURF Research Cloud needs to be connected to the EOSC Federation Federated Helpdesk, but actually the SURF Servicedesk needs to be connected.

⁵⁰ <https://servicedesk.surf.nl/wiki/display/WIKI/Service+status>

⁵¹ <https://servicedesk.surf.nl/wiki/display/WIKI/Service+status>

⁵² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8333926>

⁵³ <https://servicedesk.surf.nl>

Federating Capability	Classification	Description
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Helpdesk federating capability supports different integration options⁵⁴. The different integration options need to be assessed to analyse the best way to connect the SURF Servicedesk to the Helpdesk federating capability. Also the SURF support processes need to be aligned with the EOSC Federation support processes.
Service Management System	Recommended	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SURF has implemented an Information Security Management System (ISMS)⁵⁵. A number of SURF services are ISO 27001:2022⁵⁶ certified, including SURF Research Cloud and HPC Cloud. SURF has an internal program to implement IT Service Management (ITSM) according to FitSM family standard, compatible with ISO/IEC 20000-1 and ITIL.

If SURF Research Cloud is used as a platform for an EOSC Node it can be concluded from Table 5 that not only SURF Research Cloud capabilities need to be connected to the federating capabilities but also SURF internal business services and processes (e.g. Service Portfolio, IdM, Accounting, Monitoring, Customer Support, Servicedesk and SMS) need to be connected and aligned with the EOSC Federation Federating Capabilities.

7. Recommendations

Section 6 provides a comparison between the EOSC EU node and the planned SURF pilot node at the level of the capabilities of the platform and the services offered through the platform. If SURF is going to build a node platform capable of joining the EOSC Federation, SURF needs to align the node capabilities and processes with the EOSC Federating Capabilities. From section 6 it can be concluded that some of the node capabilities on the basis of SURF Research Cloud (e.g. user dashboard, interactive notebook, VM, container, credit system, integration with an EFSS⁵⁷ service) are comparable to the EOSC EU Node capabilities, not going into implementation technical details. But it can also be concluded that EOSC EU Node offers some additional generic capabilities. Therefore, some of the SURF internal services and processes need to be aligned with the EOSC EU Node Tier-1 services and with the EOSC Federating Capabilities. From the comparisons the following recommendations can be provided.

Recommendations for Node development

The following recommendations need to be taken into account when the SURF services are used to build up a node capable of joining the EOSC Federation. To be able to join the EOSC Federation a Node needs to be compliant to the EOSC Federation Policies and the Federating Capabilities.

- Within SURF, a modular design has been chosen in which services must be able to work independently and modularly. Services such as the Data Repository service, Filesender, Research Drive, Yoda Hosting, Archive, Backup, SURFsoc, are all independent services that can also function as part of the planned SURF pilot node. Dutch organisations can determine which services and which combination of services are made available to their affiliated researchers. Within SURF a strategic decision needs to be made to establish a coherent overlay platform providing access to services and data supporting research in the Netherlands, capable of joining the EOSC Federation.
- SURF Research Cloud does not offer a public catalogue through which researchers can request and/or access SURF services. The SURF website does not allow direct access and provisioning. Within SURF Research Cloud the current catalogue is only available through the user dashboard, after logging in.

⁵⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7308617>

⁵⁵ <https://www.surf.nl/en/information-security-surf-services>

⁵⁶ <https://www.iso.org/standard/27001>

⁵⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Enterprise_file_synchronization_and_sharing

My SURF (Mijn SURF⁵⁸) is a platform for member institutions to manage their portfolio of products and services from SURF. It is only accessible for assigned delegates from the member institutes. For a full node integration, SURF should consider offering an additional channel allowing researchers to request access to SURF services, or beyond (e.g. National and/or EOSC services), supporting research more directly.

- If SURF Research Cloud is used as a technical EOSC Node platform through which third-party services are on-boarded from the Netherlands to the EOSC Federation, local processes and criteria need to be defined to onboard services into the Node.
- The aim of the EOSC Federation is to enable the *Web of FAIR data and Services* and to lower the barrier to share and access research data and services to support research in Europe. Because services are in general nationally and/or institutionally funded, SURF should develop criteria and conditions under which national funded services can be offered to the EOSC Federation. This is especially required for volume-based or (scarce) expertise bound services.

Recommendations for technical development

The SURF portfolio contains several services that can be integrated to function as a coherent node, interoperable with the EOSC Federation. SURF Research Cloud has been developed as a platform to provide easy access to cloud resources (e.g. VMs, containers, interactive notebooks) from different cloud providers. While providing access to cloud resources is an important capability of the EOSC EU Node, the EOSC EU Node enables access to more services. To further align the planned SURF pilot node and SURF services with the EOSC EU Node the following technical developments can be taken into account.

- To improve the discoverability, access and service provision of services supporting research at SURF, and/or in the Netherlands a public service catalogue can be developed. The public service catalogue should include a channel to request access and resources aligned with National and EOSC access rules and policies.
- To improve the discoverability of research products within the SURF pilot node, e.g. the Netherlands Research Portal, based on the OpenAIRE Knowledge Graph, can be integrated into the public view of the planned SURF pilot node
- To allow automatic scale-out from SURF computing resources (e.g. HPC, HTC, Cloud) to EOSC Federation computing resources, the SURF pilot node can be integrated with the workload and infrastructure manager (AWM) offered by the EOSC EU Node.
- SURF Research Cloud provides options to enable access to SURF ResearchDrive in VMs, containers and interactive notebooks. A potential improvement is to provide basic file browser capabilities in the planned SURF pilot node user dashboard with a quick link to the full service, similar to the EOSC EU Node.
- To enable the automation of data transfers between data and computing services, the locally operated FTS service can be advertised as Bulk Data Transfer and integrated with the planned SURF pilot node or assess the integration of Bulk Data Transfer service offered through the EOSC EU Node.
- To allow easy transfers of large files by researchers, a quick link with SSO to SURFfilesender can be provided through the user dashboard of the planned SURF pilot node, similar to how Filesender has been integrated within the EOSC EU Node.
- Education, training and support in Open Science and FAIR best practices has always been a key element in EOSC to develop the necessary expertise. To support education and training within the EOSC Federation provides the EOSC EU node access to a Moodle based training platform operated by OpenAIRE, called OpenPlato⁵⁹. In collaboration with LCRDM, e-Science Center and RDNL, SURF has developed the Taxila⁶⁰ service. Taxila is the national service providing an overview of training, learning, and teaching materials for trainers and trainees. To support researchers in providing easy access to

⁵⁸ <https://mijn.surf.nl>

⁵⁹ <https://openplato.eu>

⁶⁰ <https://www.taxila.nl/>

training material and courses, the SURF pilot node website can provide a quick link to the Taxila service.

- To connect to the Helpdesk federating capability the SURF Servicedesk and user support processes need to be aligned with the EOSC Federation support processes. This requires that the SURF Servicedesk is able to connect to external helpdesk systems.
- SURF Knowledge Base service status is a wiki page that is manually maintained by the service teams. To improve and automate service availability and reliability monitoring and to make service monitoring more user centric SURF could adopt the EOSC EU Node monitoring system or adopt the ARGO monitoring system locally and publish monitoring figures in the EOSC EU Node monitoring system.
- To connect to the Accounting federating capability, the Central Budgeting and Accounting (CBA) system needs to be able to publish usage numbers for those projects/contracts coming forth through the EOSC Federation.
- To connect to the Order Management federating capability SURF customer support services and processes need to be aligned with the Order Management process adopted within the EOSC Federation. At the time of this writing, the SURF internal business services and processes are architecturally being redesigned, the requirement to connect SURF business processes and internal services to external platforms needs to be taken into account.

Recommendations for the EOSC Federation

While in the previous paragraphs list recommendations to improve SURF Research Cloud as a node platform, in this paragraph recommendations are provided to improve the EOSC Federation Federating Capabilities.

- SURF Research Cloud and the Research Capacity Computing Service⁶¹ make use of a credit system to account for the resource usage, similar to account usage on the EOSC EU Node. This can be further developed as an EOSC Federation wide credit system to support the exchange of resources within the federation.
- SURF Research Cloud (through SRAM) and the EOSC EU Node make use of a group management system to manage access and budget to resources across a group of users. These group management systems are differently implemented and are incompatible with each other. The EOSC Federation should develop group management to a federative capability in which group information to which a user belongs can be easily shared across nodes and can be implemented into node infrastructure proxies and services, for example see AARC guideline *G069 AARC-G069 Guidelines for expressing group membership and role information*⁶².
- To allow access to resources from different nodes researchers need to register themselves at the different nodes. For example, to access the resources provided through the EOSC EU Node the researcher needs to register him/herself at the EOSC EU node, and vice-versa at SURF Research Cloud. The EOSC Federation should prevent a researcher from needing to register him/herself at different nodes to access resources within the federation. A researcher just needs to register him/herself to a node once (e.g. node of preference) to allow access to all resources a researcher has access to in the federation. This requires federation wide user profiles in which group information, access, budget, usage and entitlements to resources and research products is being maintained.
- The initial Federating Capabilities as defined in section 3 can be seen as foundational federating capabilities to support the EOSC Federation to operate but does not automatically federate the resources made available through the federation, for example cloud, computing, data and storage resources, for example:
 - Federating the File Sync and Share services (EFSS) to allow researchers to easily share data with researchers across different EFSS services.

⁶¹ <https://www.surf.nl/en/research-capacity-computing-service>

⁶² <https://aarc-community.org/guidelines/aarc-g069/>

- Federating computing resources to allow automatic scale-outs of workloads and workflows across computing services offered by different nodes
- Federating data orchestration workflow systems to support the processing and analysis of data across nodes, supporting data movement to applications and the movement of applications to data.
- To make SURF Research Cloud and the EOSC EU Node Virtual Machines component compatible/interoperable and allow the movement of VMs between SURF Research Cloud and EOSC EU Node and visa-versa, consensus needs to be found on which virtual machine templates to be supported within the federation. At time of this writing the EOSC EU Node supports TOSCA templates while SURF Research Cloud Terraform templates.
- In December 2024, EuroHPC JU signed a contract to develop the EuroHPC Federation Platform, to integrate supercomputing, AI systems, quantum computing & data resources across Europe⁶³. At the time of this writing, it is not clear how the EuroHPC Federation Platform is related to the EOSC Federation. It is essential for researchers to seamlessly use EOSC and EuroHPC resources, to be able to scale-up and/or -down from EOSC to and from EuroHPC computing resources and/or to support data transfers between both federations.

8. Conclusions

From the comparison made in section 6 it can be concluded that the cloud virtual machine, container and jupyter notebook, the seamless access to these services and the credit system to account for resources in the planned SURF pilot node are comparable with the capabilities provided through the EOSC EU Node. It also provides seamless access to ResearchDrive and Webdav accessible storage systems on cloud computing nodes similar as the EOSC EU Node provides seamless access to the File Sync & Share service onto EOSC EU Node virtual machines, containers and Jupyter notebooks. Looking at how SURF Research Cloud is used as a starting point to build the SURF pilot node this cannot be seen as a surprise.

Next to these comparable capabilities, SURF Research Cloud is also missing tightly integrated capabilities which are offered by the EOSC EU Node, for example as a public service and research product discovery portal, data transfer services as filesender and/or the FTS service and access to a training platform. Therefore, SURF Research Cloud by itself is not sufficient to enable a node capable of joining the EOSC Federation, more services and capabilities are needed which are (mostly) enabled by other SURF services. SURF offers a research data discovery portal through the Netherlands Research Portal based on the OpenAIRE Knowledge Graph, offers large data transfer capabilities through the SURFfilesender service and offers access to training material through the Taxila portal. These services are currently being offered as individual services and not as an integrated component of SURF Research Cloud. If SURF Research Cloud is used as a node platform serving Dutch researchers comparable to the EOSC EU Node, a strategic decision has to be made to change the scope of SURF Research Cloud to a generic node platform. This requires future development and additional funding to further develop SURF Research Cloud as an generic node platform and to integrate the aforementioned services into the platform and user dashboard.

To develop the SURF pilot node as a node capable of joining the EOSC Federation, the SURF internal business processes and services need to be compliant to the EOSC Federation Policies and connected to the Federating Capabilities. During the build up phase of the EOSC Federation it will become clear how the SURF internal business processes and services need to be adapted to make them compliant with the EOSC Federation Policies and Capabilities.

⁶³ https://eurohpc-ju.europa.eu/paving-way-eurohpc-federation-platform-2024-12-19_en